

Public summary
Yearly Activity Report
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Aclima

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1. Summary of the context and overall objectives of the project

The amount of waste generated by households in the EU-28 was 243 million tons in 2015, which is about 9 % of the overall generation of municipal and industrial waste. Most of waste (63%) derives from construction and demolition, mining and quarrying, but household waste despite being only 9% can generate a high environmental impact if disposed to landfill.

Each person in the EU generated 475 kg of municipal waste every year, ranging from 759 kg per capita in Denmark to 272 kg per capita in Poland and Romania.

It has a very high political profile because of its complex character, due to its composition, its distribution among many sources of waste, and its link to consumption patterns. The management of this waste cost billions for our public budgets. Overall, 26% of municipal waste is still sent to landfill, 27% incinerated and only 47% of municipal waste in EU is composted or recycled. Looking at the already existing local best practices, it is possible to reach 80% recycling.

This means that 80 million tons of recyclable materials are thrown away or 'wasted' annually. Even more may come from the industrial sector.

Among recyclables, biowaste (and especially food waste) is the most sensitive fraction but it is currently separately collected only in a few Member States.

The sector contributing the most to food waste is households (47 million tonnes). About 75% of food waste may be avoidable. Composting would allow to store carbon in the soil, improving fertility and offsetting industrial GHG emissions.

Furthermore, waste management accounted for over 3% of total GHG emissions in Europe (over 100 million tons of GHG).

We need to treat waste as a valuable resource, shifting away from final treatment and disposal models towards a recycling and recovery model, based on the principles of the Circular Economy.

The EU action plan for the Circular Economy and waste framework Directive aims to improve waste management practices, stimulate recycling and innovation in materials management, and limit the use of landfilling. New ambitious goals have been proposed by 2030 to move forward a new management paradigm such as:

- Need to Increase Overall Recycling rate of municipal waste to 70%
- Obligation to introduce separate collection of biowaste aimed at the generation of high quality compost and digestate

- a food waste reduction target of 30% by 2025 and of 50 % by 2030 compared to the 2014 baseline;
- Need reduce landfill to a maximum of 10% of total waste.

To realize the potential of this model we need to improve the waste management systems across European countries.

The aim of Waste4Think project is to meet these challenges testing the effectiveness of new eco-innovative solutions (technological and non-technological) to prevent: waste generation, enhance collection, and increase the treatment, recycling and recovery of high-grade valuable materials from waste.

These Eco-innovative solutions will be developed and tested in real-life environments, 4 urban areas in Europe, the highly industrialized village of Zamudio (Spain) that uses a separated kerbside collection, the residential town of Seveso (Italy) that uses a door-to-door system, the large suburban city of Halandri (Greece) that has at the beginning of the project a very basic waste management system and the high touristic coastal town of Cascais (Portugal) with an underground collection system.

These 4 locations have different levels of industrialization and social, demographic and geographic features, as well as different realities on matters concerning waste management, the project considered 4 of them as a single integrated urban metabolism, opening the way for innovative, systemic approaches, involving the analysis of resource flows within 4 cities.

The consortium in charge of carrying out the initiative is made up of a total of 19 partners from SMEs, public agencies and universities in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Italy, Denmark and Germany.

The implementation of the solutions will have an integrated approach, covering the whole waste value chain through the establishment of a holistic methodology for data management and particularly focusing on citizen participation to build more sustainable urban areas.

The aim is to demonstrate the value of integrating eco-innovative solutions, economic, social and environmental dynamics, in a way to better understand the socio-economically and gender nuanced patterns of resource use and consumption, and pinpoint drivers of waste-avoiding behaviour, improving in the same way public governance and business models related to waste management moving towards a circular economy model.

The project aims to obtain measurable results with the integration of these solutions across the four pilots:

- Reduction of waste generation (8%),
- Increase of urban waste sorting (20%),
- Waste management costs savings (10%),
- Reduction of GHG emissions (10%)
- Waste diverted to landfill around a 23% of reduction

1.1. Brief presentation of the Work Plan

WASTE4THINK is coordinated by the Institute of Technology DeustoTech from the University of Deusto (Spain) and structured in nine work packages (WPs) to achieve an efficient realisation of the project's objectives.

Pilots Planning and execution is handled in **WP1**. The objective of this work package is twofold. On the one hand, this work package contains all the actions to define the requirements and setup the pilots sites. On the other hand, in this WP the impact achieved with the technological and non-technological actions deployed in the pilot site will be monitored.

The main objective of **WP2 “Development of Computer Assisted Integral Waste Management Systems”** is to develop IT tools in order to support waste managers in the operation and planning systems under sustainability criteria. For this, an appropriate waste data management platform will be deployed to retrieve, store and exploit recorded data, optimizing the integral waste management in a holistic way taking into consideration socio-economic variables (including gender dimension), the generation patterns and geospatial information.

These IT tools will provide the building blocks to construct the rest of the solutions of the project allowing to retrieve the information needed and to monitor the impact of the actions implemented. Finally, an incentive planner will be also implemented to foster the adoption of circular economy solutions.

The objective of **WP3 “Implementation of alternatives for the recovery of high-grade materials”** is to demonstrate, within the circular economy context, innovative approaches for waste streams that are currently either handled in non-optimized way or diverted to landfills. In more specific, the main principles of circular economy will be applied upon kitchen wastes, disposable nappies and expired food products providing products of high value and/or energy decreasing thus their diversion ratio to landfills.

The activities within **WP4 “Creation of Innovative Social Actions”** are to:

- Define new social actions to promote prevention and citizen empowerment

- Implement a set of teaching units and serious games to increase the impact of the social actions and foster mutual learning
- Carry out a citizen science activity for the co-creation of innovative eco-design solutions
- Design 3 Apps to foster transparency and citizen engagement

WP5 “Definition of new Economical Instruments” is to set up proper regulations and incentive schemes, at a municipal level, aimed at introducing innovative Pay-as you –Throw ‘PAYT’ systems or other penalty/reward schemes in the most effective way according to the collection scheme to be implemented.

WP6 “Exploitation of Eco-innovative solutions” is in charge of identifying and exploiting the most market ready results in order to introduce the eco-innovative solutions deployed and tested in the project into the market allowing connections among other cities and potential investors interested in the solutions to achieve sustainable urban environments.

The objectives of **WP7 “Dissemination and Communication”** are to:

- Implement an ambitious Dissemination and Communication Plan to set up and manage an effective communication strategy and to guarantee the public coverage of the project results at the pilot level.
- Promote the project at a wider level organizing different events, participating in top level conferences, fostering cooperation among the projects funded within this call to engage citizen, public administrations, stakeholders, the scientific community and other EU initiatives and platforms.

Knowledge and information transfer through multiple channels and networks will be centrally coordinated and managed by **WP8 “Project Management”**.

Finally, **WP9 “Ethics”** is in charge of the ethical issues that affect the project.

2. Work performed from the beginning of the project to the end of the period

The project started officially in June 2016 and the work performed and main results achieved in this first year of the project are the following ones:

2.1. WP1: Pilots planning and execution

The following actions have been carried out within this WP in this first year of the project:

2.1.1. Task 1.2. Pilots preparation

A comprehensive review of the legislation currently in force on the four pilot sites have been carried out. Moreover, the administrative formalities needed to allow the development of the actions of the project have been carried on. Finally, several dynamics have been carried out among the pilots sites to define the portfolio of Key Performance Indicators to track the progress of the project. They will cover aspects on the three pillars of the sustainability (economical, environmental and social) as well as technical aspects.

2.1.2. Task 1.2. Pilots planning

In this task comprises the creation of all design documents of the project. Several documents have been created with participation of all the partners in the consortium:

- More than 20 users groups have been defined
- More than 50 users stories have been created
- More than 100 functional requirements have been defined
- More than 20 components have been identified
- The conceptual architecture for the four pilots have been settled

Moreover, the data model and the communication interfaces among the different components have been defined. In both cases the standards of the FIWARE platforms have been extended to completely cover all the aspects needed in the project. Finally, the developing environment have been deployed and the databases with static information (geographical information, socio-economic data, etc.) are being collected, curated and populated.

2.1.3. Task 1.3. Sustainability Modelling

Within this task the creation of the baseline model have been started. To this end the four pilots are retrieving the information needed to estimate their current state of the portfolio of Key Performance Indicators defined in Task 1.1. For this purpose, several questionnaires have been sent to the citizenship and to the different stakeholders.

2.2. WP2: Development of Computer Assisted Integral Waste Management Systems

2.2.1. Task 2.1. Sensor Platform

2.2.1.1. MOBA platform improvements

The platform is subject to constant improvement. So far, on the Filling Level Sensors (FLS) part, a variety of upgrades have been made in order to get a better performance and user experience.

Mainly, the changes have been focused on easing the daily work of the office clerk and make it more user friendly.

- The filling level is displayed in the application both in a report and in the map. The design has improved considerably and there are some display configuration options.
- Now the user can create, edit and link each sensor to the correspondent garbage bin.
- The configuration of each sensor is also available for the user in a simpler manner.
- The filling level brings important data to the tour planning. It can help the office clerk to decide which bins must be included/discarded in the tour depending on their filling level. Again, the visual presentation has significantly improved.

2.2.1.2. Filling level sensors at Cascais

Filling level sensors are already installed in the bins of Cascais pilot. In addition, they are integrated with Mawisu2 (the software for monitoring and optimizing PAYT) so that office clerks can see and use the data from the sensors.

2.2.1.3. Integration between MOBA and Sotkon for Cascais Chambers

The initial meeting between Sotkon (Cascais pilot's supplier of equipment (bins) and MOBA was held to discuss basic information and possibilities. However, the integration is still pending until MOBA can test and validate the developments made in the application. Such developments will commence real soon and it is expected to have the first version by the end of 2017.

2.2.2. Task 2.2. Software Platform

2.2.2.1. Chamber system

The chambers will provide the collection company with information of the "openings" of the bin. It is an access control system that counts how many usages the citizens do for each bin by means of RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) technology. The software is under development and it is expected to be released an initial version before the end of the year 2017.

2.2.2.2. MOBA platform improvements

Big improvements have been made in terms of performance and user experience throughout the different parts of the application Mawisu2. Some of them are visible and some others are not detectable by the user since they affect in the performance (background). In addition, part of the upgrade is intended to let MOBA make future improvements on the backbone of the application.

- GUI improvements – New Sencha migration to version 6.0.2

- UNICODE support
- New charts (like 3D Pie charts)
- Mirroring effect (Right to Left) for some languages
- New controls, properties and methods over existing ones
- New format of the forms
 - Horizontal layout of the form tabs
 - Inclusion of print button to avoid some extra steps for reporting
 - Redesign of the form (toolbars, captions, colored borders to indicate user changes, new icons, drop-down menu to access different forms, map layout)
- Dashboard add-ons
- Sensor alerts and notifications

2.2.3. Task 2.3. Waste collection optimization

2.2.3.1. Task 2.3.2. Mobile IP (MIP) Communication Back-end software

The current status of implementation of additional functionalities in the MIP since the start of the Waste4think project are the following add-ons:

- Unification of families in one center to avoid Socket communication on the server for a better memory management and to allow to handle several fleets on one server.
- Remote support for mobile devices with:
 - File access on all CAN devices via web service
 - File transfer (upload and download) with the handling of interrupted GSM connection
 - Remote screen and keyboard for the MOBA Operand and CG1
 - Atomic Update, which means a script of several steps to allow an automatic update with a lot of components in one step for all connected devices.
 - The download of log file from CG1 via the file transfer
 - Automatic analysis of log file after the download
 - Tunnel of a CAN trace via REST – Web service direct in Office
 - Multi-client capability to allow the data transfer for up to 8 clients in parallel
 - New tools for emptying reports

2.2.3.2. Task 2.3.3. Mobile device Mini operand and firmware

This task is in accordance to the project plan.

The status is the finished design for the housing of the device. The samples are available as a 3D printed housing.

Mini operand in the cradle

just the cradle

The construction of the casting mold is in progress.

We expect the first samples for the pilot until the end of 2017.

In the meanwhile, the application software is in development. The running tasks are the implementation of the MOBA-specific hardware driver in the WINCE operation system.

This is valid for the CAN hardware, the RFID reader, the barcode scanner, the camera and the power management.

The basic module with the standard operating system is already running.

2.2.3.3. MOBA Platform improvements

The scope has been defined in order to make clear of which improvements MOBA plans to include. Some developments are under analysis phase, some other are being carried on and some are implemented.

Enhanced tour planning

- Online operation control monitoring (new widget)
 - Run selector
 - Results table
- Service scheduling (to assign vehicles for each shift and a service type of a tour)
 - Filter
 - Results table
- Calendar
- Grids multi-select
- Master tour in cache
- Performance

Hardware-Software integration improvements

- FollowMe (allow file creation and edition from Mawisu2 as part from the vehicle)
- Unique file integration (optimized file transfer)
- Auto-importing (speed up the file sharing process between vehicle and Mawisu2)

2.2.5. Task 2.5. Incentive System Planner to Foster Circular Economy

There have been several meetings between those in charge of designing the tool and those in charge of developing it in order to define the inputs of the tool. Once defined, database on European legislation has been created, as well as, that legislation affecting the four territories of the pilots.

A Best Practices and New Business Models database has also been created with new operational business models identified worldwide. The focus is on the identification and evaluation of best practices and new business models based on circular economy, especially in the fields of raw materials markets, bioeconomy, packaging and food waste, industrial symbiosis and new supply chains.

This database will be filled throughout the project.

2.3. WP3: Implementation of alternatives for the recovery of high-grade materials

2.3.1. Task 3.1. “Biomass product” valorization

It concerns the alternative options for the treatment and valorization of household food waste. 236 households scattered in the municipality of Halandri were selected and provided with 30 L portable bins, biodegradable bags, information flyer with magnet and a key to a 120 L bins located near their residence. The 120 L bins have been collected using a truck equipped with appropriate weighing and data transmission devices.

A pilot-scale drying and shredding facility was developed at the Municipality of Halandri. The collected food waste has been dried and shredded to generate a food residue biomass product (FORBI). FORBI has been completely characterized. The necessary analytical and lab-scale reactor equipment was acquired and commissioned by NTUA and a pelletizer was acquired by the Municipality.

At NTUA preliminary experiments were carried out for the production of methane through anaerobic digestion, biohydrogen through dark fermentation and bioethanol through alcoholic fermentation with different yeast strains. Experiments for the direct production of electricity from FORBI extract through microbial fuel cells were carried out. Composting of FORBI was also carried out using both a closed-vessel lab-scale composter and a 280 composting bin. Pellets were generated from FORBI and

characterized. A preliminary analysis of the suitability of FORBI as an alternative fuel for the cement industry was carried out. Finally, experiments for the production of biosorbent from FORBI have started.

2.3.2. Task 3.2. Disposable nappies and expired food product valorization

During the first year of the project's implementation, Green Technologies Ltd in collaboration with University of Patras have collected all the needed information from Super Markets regarding the expired food products that are not handled in a sustainable way. They determined the representative sample of these expired food products and performed a detailed physicochemical characterization.

The same was applied for the disposable nappies (both from nurseries and elderly houses). The physicochemical characterization was followed by an extensive study on the optimization of the pretreatment methods for these waste streams, in order to proceed in anaerobic digestion trials. The lab scale experiments on the optimization of H₂ and CH₄ production have been completed and Green Technologies Ltd is ready to take the next step and upgrade the pilot-scale Waste Treatment Unit and proceed with up-scale tests before the implementation of the unit in Municipality of Halandri (Greece).

In the frame of circular economy and having in mind that every waste is a potential raw material that could be further valorized to obtain new products, there are ongoing tests for the treatment of the anaerobic effluent sludge and the production of compost. Bilateral meetings also took place, with researchers, stakeholders and companies in the field of plastics for the valorization of the recovered plastics from disposable nappies.

2.4. WP4: Creation of innovative Social Actions

During the first year of the Waste4Think project, where the five major tasks have been initiated, the primary focus of WP4 has been the generation of the pilots social programme and developing four serious games to support this. The objective of this work package is to foster behavioral change in waste producers.

2.4.1. Task 4.1. Generation of the pilot's social programme

In order to define the Social Actions Program for each pilot, a questionnaire was prepared and sent to all the partners to describe the environmental education strategies that are going to be developed in each municipality. The objectives, target groups, key messages, specific actions, means and human resources and also the indicators and monitoring needs were deeply defined.

These contents were discussed in the Cascais meeting (December, 2016) and also in some workshops, suggesting some changes or new actions. The use of the ICT tools in the framework of the social strategies has been of special relevance. All the actions and monitoring methodology has been summarized in the Social Action Plan.

Some of the actions have already started, also the social baseline has been calculated in two of the pilots.

2.4.2. Task 4.2. Learning materials

During this first year, several meetings took place with pilot sites involved in the use of innovative ICT solutions for learning (Zamudio and Halandri) to better understand their needs and provide a value added solution in the learning process about waste management.

As a result of the surveys and interviews carried out with these schools, the outcome digital project structure will be flexible and adaptable to the wide range of needs of schools.

The relevance of the learning materials has also been recognized by other pilots sites – Cascais and Seveso - (no directly involved in the testing, at first sight) who are also willing to participate in the educational experience.

At this stage, Virtualware is working on the design of a matrix that allows the disintegration and at the same time the grouping of educational materials in a simple and intuitive way. This matrix has been validated by schools in order to fit their needs and possibilities.

After the conversations held with all the agents involved, finally 6 educational itineraries were selected (including 4 STEAM lessons and 4 Mobile games). The digital educational project includes the use of technology as a tool for facilitating learning processes. In these specific projects, online content and references will be used to reinforce specific knowledge about waste management and free digital tools to create new content by students and teachers. In these digital projects, analog actions or analog alternatives will be included due to the lack of appropriate devices (computers, tablets ...) in some schools.

The objective is twofold, on the one hand to seek information from reliable sources to improve knowledge about the different subjects and on the other hand to learn how to use that information to generate new quality contents.

From the surveys carried out in the schools, 7 topics have been extracted as the most interesting ones for schools covering a wide range of aspects related with waste management;

Waste or Resource (monitoring, Waste generation,...)	Decision making
First step: Prevention, Separate or not separate	Reusability
Separate or not separate	Division, Monitoring, Analysis
Avoid Food wastage	Measurement, Concept, Prevention, Correction
Composting	Concept and associated biological and

	physical chemical processes. Measurement of data Analysis Production
Waste Ecosystems	Values Impacts Analysis and reflection Action
The true cost of waste	Impact on the environment Present actions for the future. Local actions with global impact

These topics will in some cases be treated as the main theme of digital projects or as cross-cutting themes (that is, they may appear within a digital project as part of it, but not as a main theme).

For the definition of the first STEAM a problem situation has been raised, to which the students must respond with the available resources.

NAME PROJECT DIGITAL	After the concert
PROJECT DESCRIPTION	Detective game.
Village festivals are taking place. You have come down to the square to participate in the theater workshops that are organized. On arrival you find a lot of "waste". The workshops have been canceled. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and resolve this case.	

This draft will be presented to the schools to receive their impressions and improve it or modify it according to your feedback. The objective is to know if it is applicable in the classroom, if they believe that it will motivate the students and the teaching staff and if the structure proposed is adequate.

From this contrast, the first STEAM and first Digital Project will be finally defined and completed. The recommendations received will be applied to the definition and development of the remaining digital projects.

2.4.3. Task 4.3. Serious Games

The four games to support behavioural change across different user groups have been initiated and are progressing with slight delays in two of the games.

- Sorting Game:

Creating awareness for youth by showing them principles of sorting waste.

Workshops have defined the concept and scope. The design and technical specifications are done. We have recently announced a playable prototype and are now working towards a beta version. Recently new graphics have been proposed, hopefully making the pictures easier to decode quickly. There has been interest in using the Sorting Game across all participating pilots, some later this year.

- Eco Design Game:

Make design and engineering students aware of the waste impact of design, process and material choice. Make design choices based on market demand.

Workshops have defined the concept and scope. The design and technical specifications are done. A playable prototype is available and we expect a beta version soon.

A process to develop and create data and cases in collaboration with Halandri pilot and university students is expected to begin soon. Next use case for the game is expected to be diapers.

- Virtual City Game:

University students (and more) can experience and play the principles of circular economy and see the effects of sustainability and environment. Workshops have defined the concept and scope. The design and technical specifications are done.

Basic programming has been done on the game, but game design and mechanics are still being developed. In the process of acquiring, validating and implementing data. Prototype expected later this year.

- Planning Game:

Let citizens experience the complexity of city waste management.

You set the strategy and see the impact of your decisions.

The user group for this game has changed. To accommodate these changes, we are currently developing concept, scope and game design. Expecting to finish game design and concept later this year and a prototype early next year.

2.4.5. Task 4.5. Implementation of the Apps

The apps development is still in the beginning. We have been working in the validation of the functional requirements and use cases, and the extraction of the low level and third-party technological requisites.

We are composing the technical documentation of the apps. The content of these documents is based in the technological requisites from pilot stakeholders.

We are also studying and describing the protocol to connect the apps with FI-WARE infrastructure and with other Waste4think developments.

In parallel, we have created the design documents of the apps describing the features that we will develop in the apps implementation. These documents also include some open questions that consortium partners are still debating about.

2.5. WP5: Definition of new Economical Instruments

2.5.1. Task 5.1. New PAYT schemes

The data model to calculate the PAYT schemes has been defined for the pilot of Seveso, with specific parameters. Through the analysis of the boundary conditions and variables affecting parameters and through interviews to providers that allow bin/bag identification, indicators to measure the effectiveness of the readings are being preliminarily identified. Examples of PAYT model have been chosen to be inserted as Best Practices in the Database, foreseen in Deliverable D1.2.

2.5.2. Task 5.2. Definition of specific PAYT systems on pilots

Seveso introduced the new PAYT system: the regulation has been approved on 30th March by the Municipal Council. Specific information campaigns have been dedicated to citizens, in order to drive them through the change. Some specific meetings have been dedicated to the other municipalities, Zamudio and Cascais (Halandri is not committed to introduce PAYT), in order to evaluate the possibility of implementing PAYT and to assist them in the choice of PAYT model to apply and to write the related regulation. In particular, Zamudio started the participative process about PAYT and Cascais is developing its own model. Furthermore a workshop on PAYT has been held during the Green Week 2017, on 9th May at Deusto University in Bilbao. At the workshop a panel of experts, including Michele Giavini, spoke about PAYT most common methodologies and their spread in European countries. The workshop was available also in streaming (W4T You Tube channel) and it has been registered in Spanish and English to easy the comprehension by the broad public.

2.5.3. Task 5.3. Invoicing integration

The preparation of invoicing module, starting from the outcome of Task 5.1, is in progress. For Seveso, an existing invoicing software, based on the parameters decided in the new local regulation, has been used; it will be improved during the project, and a specific integration into a website will be delivered by the end of 2017. The full implementation for all the municipalities is foreseen by the end of the project.

2.6. WP6: Exploitation of Eco-innovative solutions

During the first year of the Project, the five activities included in the WP6 have been launched. The most significant achievements are summarized as follows:

2.6.1. Task 6.2. Identification of key results and functional analysis of each key result

Based on the 20 eco-innovative results previously identified in the Grant Agreement, specific forms for the project have been launched to establish a first functional and value innovation analysis of business ideas in terms of the strength of the idea, industry, market, financial issues as well as staff involved. These are the five pillars on which successful business ideas are based. 8 forms were received corresponding to 7 eco-innovative results. After a qualitative analysis of the information provided, some areas of improvement have been detected in all the forms received. An individualized work with each partner, has allowed to reinforce the detected weaknesses and to move to the next phase.

2.6.2. Task 6.4. IPR analysis

In every exploitation plan, it is necessary and decisive to define the best strategy of protection of results that best suits the commercial, technical and scientific objectives of every partner within the project. In this sense, new questionnaires have been already launched to all partners of the project in order to define as accurately as possible the necessary background for both, the implementation and the exploitation of the project, as well as to analyse the foreground that will be generated in the framework of W4T. In this sense, it is possible to anticipate any conflicts of interest that may arise among partners and outline optimal protection strategies that facilitate the exploitation of all the detected business ideas.

2.6.3. Task 6.5. Development of business models, business plans and exploitation action plans

Four of the forms received showed sufficient strength in the five pillars previously described and have moved on to a second phase focused on the design of the business model. The tool used for this purpose has been another form focused on specifying the 9 sections of the canvas model.

One of the forms received is in a position to design the final Canvas Model and begin with the description of the business plan.

2.7. WP7: Dissemination and Communication

Communication plays an integral role in keeping a project on task. During the first year of the project this work package has been of great importance since the Personal Brand of the project has been defined. These are the main activities carried out:

2.7.1. Task 7.1. Elaboration and update of the dissemination and communication plans

In the first six months of the project The Dissemination and Communication Plan was drafted which details the communication strategy to be carried out throughout the project.

2.7.2. Task 7.2. Creation of common communication and dissemination materials

A logo and a specific corporate image was designed at the beginning of the project. WASTE4THINK logo is the peculiar element to easily identify the project.

A number of templates with the corporate image were developed together with the different communication materials: brochure, leaflet, posters, roll-up with public presentation (ppt template for general project).

2.7.3. Task 7.3. On-line tools for communication and dissemination

The website of the project was created with links to partners' websites so that it gives more opportunities to the users to find information and to deepen into project's contents. It is always being updated with appointments, documents, videos, photos and materials for media in order to be social and communicative.

In addition, different profiles of Social Media have been created to set up and feed the community of stakeholders and encourage its members to actively participate on the project issues and topics. Specifically, Twitter profile as a direct dissemination channel, LinkedIn profile for publication of contents to facilitate a more professional and personalised conversation and Facebook to raising awareness on the advances of the project.

The first Newsletter was released on February used both to target interested researchers with relevant news and presenting the results and companies in the project and also as a basis for communications with the public.

2.7.4. Task 7.4. Clustering activities

Other projects funded within this H2020- WASTE call have been identified.

A guide is going to be prepared to share with partners involved in this task in order to establish a strategy to share experiences and exchange information among their pilots, see the progress of their activities and analyse the responses of the stakeholders in the pilots.

2.7.5. Task 7.5. Communication campaigns for pilots

Different activities have been carried out addressing citizens, such as social events to explain the project, eco-events with dishwashers or compostable materials,..

A press released was published in different media with the kick-off meeting and also several releases at pilot level.

A general video of the project has been produced describing the project, its objectives and expected impacts with a brief description of the four pilots.

3. Pilots status

In this first year of the project, the pilots have progressed carrying out different actions.

3.1. Cascais pilot

The Waste 4 Think test Pilot of Cascais started with an assessment of waste collection needs and potential routes for optimized service and reduced costs. This is particularly relevant as the PAYT system brings a new approach on how citizens use the service and interact with the equipment. Simultaneously, we promoted a baseline assessment of waste production to understand the starting point on the test area. The waste production and recycling rates are fundamental indicators of the system's success.

The equipment analysis concluded the need to implement 88 new underground bins with larger capacity with the PAYT card system imbued in the opening door / mechanism. This means that the 2500 inhabitants of Bairro dos Lombos Sul and Quinta de São Gonçalo would now become automatically eligible to use the equipment voluntarily on a first stage. It is particularly relevant to provide an easy and comfortable use of the equipment to promote the new system.

The placement of the bins was challenging as the test area is an urban neighbourhood with continuous demand for space, waste bins (and service) where daily activities must be ensured. As this action concluded, we moved further to the PAYT system assessment.

As the waste collection service is optimized by our "Smart Waste Management", which intends to optimize routes and bin location through data gathered from routes analysis and filling sensors, our approach needs to carefully include the PAYT collection within the existing method. There are benefits from this approach as we can analyse the PAYT savings in the system without significant changes in the collection trucks or equipment. We can also assess the impact on collection needs from the new system, meaning less costs and more comfort for residents.

We are now finalizing the economic model which translates in a "collective PAYT" system. Initially, neighbourhood performance will be assessed and the benefits for individuals will be the same to improve community engagement. However, individual production will also be estimated by the number of bin openings. Any system has its flaws and a staged implementation (from voluntary to mandatory) will follow with acceptance and use.

3.2. Halandri pilot

With the completion of the first year of the Waste4Think project, the Municipality of Halandri, in collaboration with NTUA and ENBIO applied source separation and

separate collection of the Fermentable Household Waste (FHW), aiming to generate FORBI (a Food Residue Biomass product) and to evaluate this material as potential feedstock for the production of fuels and high-grade materials.

Fermentable household waste (FHW) of Halandri municipality has been collected from 702 residents, 236 households, twice a week. Participants, following a selection process and a briefing meeting, have been provided with 30L portable household bins and biodegradable bags made of starch and leaflets with information about what can be disposed this way. Filled bags are deposited in locked 120 liter bins, proximally located. Residents handle in this manner only kitchen food waste such as cooked food waste, fruit, vegetable, used tissue paper (cellulose), except of bones and fluids. The 120 L bins are collected every three or four days by a truck, which will in the future be fueled by biogas produced from FHW, in a cyclical economy approach. The collected material is then transferred for drying and shredding in a specially designed area 24m². The material is heat-treated (92-980C) and shredded in a dryer/shredder, in order to generate a biomass product, FORBI. NTUA has started evaluating FORBI as raw material for the production of biogas (Hydrogen, Methane and HYTHANE), compost, animal feed, bioethanol, electricity, pellets, activated carbon and an alternative fuel for the cement industry. Preliminary lab scale experiments are particularly encouraging.

Presentations in scientific conferences, public events, press releases, specialized sites, and social network development have been realized.

During the first year of the project's implementation, Green Technologies Ltd in collaboration with University of Patras have collected all the needed information from Super Markets regarding the expired food products that are not handled in a sustainable way. They determined the representative sample of these expired food products and performed a detailed physicochemical characterization. The same was applied for the disposable nappies (both from nurseries and elderly houses). The physicochemical characterization was followed by an extensive study on the optimization of the pretreatment methods for these waste streams, in order to proceed in anaerobic digestion trials. The lab scale experiments on the optimization of H₂ and CH₄ production have been completed and Green Technologies Ltd is ready to take the next step and upgrade the pilot-scale Waste Treatment Unit and proceed with up-scale tests before the implementation of the unit in Municipality of Halandri (Greece). Regarding dissemination activities, there have been numerous reports in Greek newspapers, blogs and social media as well as a submission of a scientific paper in a peer reviewed journal and both oral and poster presentations in scientific conferences.

3.3. Seveso pilot

Seveso is a municipality located in Lombardy Region, with about 22.000 inhabitants. Well before the project, Seveso had a very high recycling rate, reaching around 75% in 2016 and had already introduced a RFID identification system for residual waste in order to associate each user to bags collected.

This system allowed to implement since May 2017, in the framework of Waste4Think project, the new PAYT system (Pay As You Throw) by which citizens pay a waste service tax with two components, fixed and variable. The fixed part aims to cover the basic service's cost, the variable one is now related to the effective unsorted waste produced by the user. The Municipal Council approved the regulation on PAYT on 30th

March 2017. ARS and SOFTLINE assisted the municipality of Seveso in introducing the tax and the new regulation.

The introduction of PAYT system included an awareness and sensitization campaign towards citizens.

Initially, a press conference and an evening event have been held on 12th of April for the presentation to public and media of the new regulation. In April, some activities for citizens also started, in particular the Funny door to door campaign, in which LEGAMBIENTE set up different innovative sensitization activities: a team with actors playing music and singing nice songs about waste in public places, technicians giving information to citizens about the new tax and about the right way to collect, separate and throw waste away etc. An education activity started also in schools and parishes. Furthermore, some “dinners with waste” in courtyards have been promoted: inhabitants of courtyards are invited to share some food with others and to provide washable plates and cutlery. During the dinners, operators carried on awareness games on waste and ask participants to fill a “satisfaction” survey about the new PAYT system in Seveso.

Thank also to the awareness campaign, after the PAYT introduction the separate collection rate has further improved to about 80-85%.

For late 2017 other activities have been planned. In particular, Eco-events, i.e. sustainable popular parties with low level of waste production, will start in August 2017 with the support of ARS; in September 2017, INNOVA 21 will start the promotion campaign for re-usable nappies in families with new-born and nurseries; in late autumn 2017, ARS and SEVESO municipality will promote the Virtuous household contest, in which a small number of households will be selected and undergo a very strict monitoring to improve their behavior about waste reduction.

Furthermore, the PAYT scheme could undergo light modifications in order to improve it and to maximize people acceptance.

3.4. Zamudio pilot

Zamudio is a municipality with a spread population, around 3.200 inhabitants that uses a separated kerbside collection system. Waste lorries are equipped with GPS tracking system and the bio-waste containers are equipped with a RFID lock to monitor and track the users opening the containers with a “citizen’s card”.

For the industrial waste (similar to urban wastes) the collection it is carried out regularly for mixed waste and for the other fractions only under request. The current tariff system consists on a fixed amount per household or activity.

The main goal of Waste4Think project is to improve the current waste management practices system through the implementation of new practices such as a full monitoring and decision making information system or the implementation of new economic

instruments such as PAYT to encourage citizen involvement in increasing selective waste collection and in reducing waste generation.

To achieve this, the social acceptance will be analysed and discussed by different channels of communication such as surveys, social networks, workshops and forums throughout the project, weighing their suitability for the municipality and the best way to deploy them.

During this first year of the project some of these activities have been carried out already. In particular, a survey was conducted in Zamudio at the very beginning of the project in order to learn about the habits of citizens in consumption and waste management as well as their receptivity to adopt new and more sustainable routines. Besides, a social event was held on March 2017 to introduce Waste4Think to the citizens of Zamudio and to encourage them to get involved in the project and to take part in the work groups that will set the basis for people's active involvement. The 25th of May the 1st participation workshop was held to analyze the disadvantages and possible solutions of the proposed monitoring system, including an electronic lock for different collecting containers which is being developed and weight and identification systems in bins and containers.

These technological solutions will allow not only to collect data in real time about who is sorting and who is recycling through the use of citizen card but also to improve the collection system which will permit to implement PAYT system in industry by door-to-door system.

4. Images Repository with impressions of Waste4Think

Project presentation in Halandri

Graduate students in the Department of Chemical Engineering (University of Patras) being informed

Conference about Food Waste in the Framework of Waste4Think

Project presentation in Zamudio

Meeting in Seveso to check citizens 'composting habits'

Meeting with citizens to explain the blu bags chip with RFID in Seveso

